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Chemical modification of wood in low-FA aqueous systems using kraft lignin and bark-derived products

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BACKGROUND

Wood: a material that needs protection

As a hygroscopic and biodegradable material, wood is naturally susceptible to abiotic and biotic degradation, compromising its dimensional stability, mechanical integrity and long-term service life

BACKGROUND

Industrial routes to wood protection

Wood preservatives

Biocide retention in wood
(no covalent modification)

Wood modification

Thermal modification

Thermal modification of cell wall
polymers

Acetylation

Addition-substitution reaction
with wood

Furfurylation

In situ polymerization (cell-
wall bulking + lumen filling)

Opportunities for next-generation formulations

- ✓ There is still room to increase the biobased fraction of treatment systems using existing industrial routes as a platform.
- ✓ Reduce chemical loading and energy demand while maintaining performance.
- ✓ Biobased co-reactants can add multifunctionality without changing the industrial process concept.
- ✓ **Our approach: reduce FA content using biobased co-reactants (bark extracts and Kraft lignin)**

BACKGROUND

Bark extracts and Kraft lignin: nature-derived co-reactants

Property	Extracts	Lignin
Natural abundance	5-20 wt. % (bark)	20-30 wt. %
By-product	Wood processing industry	Cellulose pulp & biorefineries
Chemistry	Oligomers with high density of Ph-OH	Complex amorphous aromatic polymer, several functional groups (OH, C=O, COOH, -OCH ₃)
Solubility	High (H ₂ O)	Low (H ₂ O) High (FA)
Antioxidant capacity	High	High/Medium
UV absorption	Moderate (short wavelengths)	High ↑ (broad spectrum)
Antimicrobial	High	Medium
Assembly capacity	Moderate	Good

Ph-OH density → radical scavenging / UV screening → stabilises surfaces
 Aromatic backbone → hydrophobicity + compatibility with furanic network

Both streams bring phenolic/aromatic functionalities: bark extracts supply bioactivity/antioxidant potential; Kraft lignin contributes broad-spectrum UV absorption and potential network densification.
Together they can extend the in-wood furanic network formed during FA polymerization

BACKGROUND

Oak bark extracts: tests as preservative agents in wood protection

Main characteristics of the extracts from oak bark

Solution	pH	[g/L]	TPC [mgGAE/g dry extract]	TFC [mgQE/g dry extract]	IC50* [ug/mL]	Main components
AQUEOUS EXTRACTION	4.8±0.3	1,67±0.1↓	25,1±0,1	33,70±0.2	50.92	Tannins, phenolics
ETHANOL-WATER EXTRACTION	5.4±0.2	8,51±0.3	120,88±4,5	95,90±0,5	16.80	Phenolics, flavanoids
ALKALINE WATER EXTRACTION	12.2±0.2	16,27±1,6	2,64±0,1↓	11.20±0.2↓	175.21↓	Phenolics, Lignin derivatives

*Lower IC₅₀ = higher antioxidant activity

Representative photographs of bark-impregnated wood samples after exposure to *T. versicolor* and *R. placenta*
 WL = mass loss after fungal exposure

Extraction route controls bioactivity: EtOH–water extracts show the highest TPC/TFC and the lowest IC₅₀ (strongest antioxidant activity), and they delivered the lowest fungal mass loss in wood. Results confirm that oak bark extracts provide relevant bioactive functionality at low concentrations.

BACKGROUND

Kraft lignin: previous tests and wood properties

Results of wood impregnated with Kraft lignin

Specimen	WPG [%]	Density [kg/m ³]	Increase in Density [%]	Product loss after leaching [%]	Product retained [%]
Pine Ref	-	437.84 (13.67)	-	-	-
Pine-L	2.15 (0.27)	450.22 (13.87)	2.14	-0.62	71.16
Beech Ref	-	741.21 (28.94)	-	-	-
Beech-L	0.81 (0.20)	749.72 (28.87)	0.77	-0.80	1.24

Herrera et al., 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15163409>

Kraft lignin adds functionality, Improved hydrophobicity and UV stability, but product retention and colour uniformity remain limited, motivating hybrid systems aimed at improved fixation and homogeneous distribution.

Wood hydrophobicity by WCA

Color changes after UV-radiation

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental workflow and formulation concept

The formulations are designed to combine FA as reactive medium + biobased co-reactants (bark extracts, Kraft lignin). The final goal is to create a low-FA hybrid formulations with tunable functionalities.

- Two bark-derived streams were produced (EtOH-H₂O UAE; alkaline)
- Hardwood Kraft lignin was pre-dissolved in FA and blended with bark fractions and organic acids (catalysis).
- Multiple low-FA hybrid formulations were screened.
- Selected formulations were evaluated on wood.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Wood impregnation and modification methodology

Low-FA aqueous formulations

Formulation	FA [wt%]	Water [wt%]	Bark extracts [wt%]	Kraft lignin [wt%]	Catalyst ¹ [wt%]
Reference	44	54	-	-	1-2
Solution A	35-40	54	2-5↑	1-4↓	1-2
Solution B	35-40	54	1-4↓	2-5↑	1-2

Ranges indicate screening space; results shown correspond to selected formulations
¹Organic acids

MODIFIED WOOD PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

- WPG
- Leachability
- Color changes
- Wettability (WCA)
- Moisture sorption

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Wood impregnation and fixation indicators

Treatment performance indicators

Formulation	WPG [%]	Volumetric swelling [%]	Bulking coefficient [%]	Bulk density [g/cm ³]	Leaching loss [%]	WPG _{final} [%]
Reference	79.1 ± 19.3	15.7 ± 0.9	12.2 ± 0.9	0.51 ± 0.03	1.97 ± 0.21	76.39 ± 18.2
Solution A	69.9 ± 10.3	15.1 ± 2.4	10.7 ± 3.8	0.56 ± 0.03	1.78 ± 0.06	68.66 ± 9.5
Solution B	56.8 ± 10.2	15.0 ± 1.9	9.3 ± 3.0	0.52 ± 0.03	2.59 ± 0.33	55.37 ± 10.1

mean ± standard deviation, n = 20

The higher leaching loss in Solution B suggests partial fixation of the lignin solution, to be addressed in further optimization.

Nevertheless, post-leaching retention and volumetric swelling remain comparable across all formulations, confirming *in situ* fixation and equivalent short-term dimensional stability with reduced FA loading.

WPG initial and after leaching

Changes in density

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical changes after modification

Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Changes from Beech wood	Band interpretation
~1733	Broadening in treated samples	C=O stretching Formation/increase of carbonyl-containing functionalities after curing. Consistent with resin formation and/or incorporation of oxygenated groups from co-reactants.
~1660–1652	Increase (more evident in treated)	C=C stretching. Supports increased conjugation/aromatic contribution after FA curing; consistent with furanic network formation and additional aromatic moieties.
~1506-1593	Broadening in treated samples	Aromatic in-plane vibrations. Reinforces presence of additional aromatic/furanic structures after treatment.
~789–787	New / increased in treated	C–H out-of-plane bending of furan ring (aromatic out-of-plane). Presence after curing (formation of in-wood furanic network).
~733	New / increased in treated	Symmetric ring bending (C–C–C) of furans. Additional support for polyfurfuryl alcohol / furanic network formation.

FTIR and PCA confirm distinct chemical modification in hybrid formulations. PCA separation confirms that hybrid formulations generate a chemically distinct wood profile from the FA reference.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Wood-water interactions

Water contact angle of wood surfaces

Formulation	WCA _{t=0} [°]	WCA _{t=60} [°]
Untreated	39.0 ± 5.39	-
Reference	102.9 ± 16.6	101.3 ± 8.8
Solution A	112.7 ± 10.3	101.0 ± 3.4
Solution B	96.0 ± 30.7	73.7 ± 4.5

mean ± standard deviation, n = 60

FA-based modification increase surface hydrophobicity and reduces moisture uptake and hysteresis vs. untreated beech, indicating improved dimensional behavior under RH cycling.

hysteresis as a function of relative humidity

DVS sorption-desorption isotherms of unmodified wood and modified samples

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Colour Changes and UV Stability

Color values of modified wood samples

Formulation	L*	a*	b*	ΔE^*
Untreated	77.1 ± 1.1	8.0 ± 0.7	26.8 ± 1.2	-
Reference	26.1 ± 1.3	7.6 ± 0.7	9.3 ± 1.4	54.01
Solution A	27.5 ± 1.3	8.9 ± 0.7	10.9 ± 1.5	52.12
Solution B	30.4 ± 1.8	9.1 ± 0.5	13.6 ± 1.6	48.62

mean ± standard deviation, n = 60

Color changes after 300 h UV-radiation

Formulation	L*	a*	b*	ΔE^*
Untreated	65.7 ± 3.1 hybrid low F	13.3 ± 0.9	36.9 ± 1.8	16.13
Reference	33.3 ± 2.0	5.8 ± 0.4	12.4 ± 0.9	8.04
Solution A	30.8 ± 1.1	5.9 ± 0.5	10.2 ± 0.8	4.52
Solution B	35.8 ± 3.5	5.6 ± 0.5	11.5 ± 1.5	6.77

mean ± standard deviation, n = 60

All treatments darkened beech wood, but the hybrid low-FA systems improved UV color stability

Appearance of modified wood samples

KEY CONCLUSIONS

- Beech was successfully impregnated with low-FA aqueous formulations where FA was partially replaced by oak bark fractions and Kraft lignin, confirming chemical changes (FTIR/PCA).
- Reducing FA lowered WPG vs FA reference, yet swelling bulking remained comparable, indicating similar volumetric stabilization after waters soaking.
- Post-leaching retention remained high overall, the lignin richer formulation (B) showed the highest leaching loss, pointing to partial fixation as the main optimization target.
- All FA-based systems increase surface hydrophobicity and reduced moisture uptake/hysteresis, supporting a more stable response under RH cycling.
- All treatments darkened wood; hybrid low-FA systems improved color stability after UV exposure.

Ongoing work: Optimize lignin fixation and validate durability (decay/thermal performance).

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Thank you for your attention!

Questions?
Comments?
Suggestions?

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